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RURAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A STUDY OF MICRO, SMALL, AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN INDIA**Dr. Satish Dhoke**

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ABSTRACT

The MSME Sector plays a crucial role in the nation's financial development and is a key conduit for establishing work opportunities with little overhead. The State Government has successfully simplified the SSI enlistment process and reduced archives properly to facilitate the quick development of SSI. The State Government amended the SSI unit plan, increasing it for the small sector up to ₹. 1 crore and increasing the venture ceiling from ₹. 50,000 to ₹. 2 lakh. In the State as of March 2000, there were 1,35,350 perpetually enrolled SSI units. These units had a creation limit of 7,50,744 lakhs and an absolute interest of 10,73,943 lakhs. Approximately 1011954 people have used all of these units. The organization offers a range of initiatives to support independent businesses with big ideas. If anyone is interested in starting a business, they should get in touch with the National Institute for Entrepreneurship and Independent Venture Advancement (NIESBUD), National Institute for Micro, Little and Medium Enterprises (NI-MSME), Indian Institute of Entrepreneurship (IIE), or the Development Chief (DC-MSME) for information on their plans. In light of the aforementioned information, this study aimed to understand the most recent developments in the MSME mechanical sector and how they affected the neighborhood's economic and environmental growth.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, regional development, Rural Development, MSME, and economic development.

I. INTRODUCTION

The majority of nations in the world have economic development as their top priority. Almost without exception, this truth is accepted. Due to India's economy's rapid expansion, the industrial For planners and policymakers, development has grown to be a major worry. Due to the ability to address issues like general poverty, unemployment, backwardness, poor production, low productivity, and a low standard of life, industrialization is crucial to the development of emerging nations. For industrialized nations, it is equally crucial to prevent cyclical swings because it not only enables them to sustain their current growth but also to enjoy even greater standards of living. Therefore, a key goal of planning in India has been the country's rapid industrial growth. India's post-independence development plans placed a strong emphasis on industrialization as a crucial tool for long-term progress. Industrial development is thought to be important for achieving high rates of economic growth, meeting the basic needs of the population, creating a more diversified economy, and bringing about institutional and social reforms. (Dangayach, G.S. and Deshmukh, S.G, 2005)

Indian Sector of Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Businesses

The MSME industry is important to the Indian economy. An economic and social catalyst. The MSME industry is important to the Indian economy. The sector, which acts as a catalyst for the nation's socioeconomic transition, is essential to achieving the national goals of increasing employment, lowering poverty, and preventing rural-to-urban migration. These businesses encourage the adoption of indigenous technologies while also contributing to the development of a vibrant entrepreneurial eco-system. Over the past few years, the sector has consistently grown. The sector has consistently grown over the past few years, but it has done so in a limited context that frequently leads to wasteful resource allocation. Inadequate access to financial resources is one of the main obstacles preventing MSMEs from expanding and developing, especially during economic downturns.

In the private sector, tiny firms are frequently referred to as "MSMEs." Regulators and financial institutions all throughout the world define the sector in the context of finance using criteria including staff strength, yearly sales, fixed asset value, and loan size proxies. For instance, in Mexico, companies with fewer than 500 employees (OECD) are regarded as MSMEs. According to the World Bank definition, a company is deemed an MSME if it satisfies two of the three requirements for classification: employee strength, asset size, or annual sales. The MSME sector is defined by the Government of India's Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise Development Act 2006 (MSMED Act). This categorization, which builds on the previous Small Scale Industry (SSI) definition, employs the investment metric to identify MSMEs because investments in machinery and equipment can be quantified and validated.

Definitions and Financial Institutions for Msme

Although investments in plant and machinery are observable and quantifiable, the existing definition offers little insight into an enterprise's financial appetite and performance. As a result, many financial institutions prefer to use yearly sales/revenue (turnover) as a major indicator for product development and risk management, as well as to segment and target MSMEs, as shown in the chart below.

Table No.1: Internal Definition Used by Banks for MSME

Enterprise Size	Micro		Small		Medium	
Institution Type	Turnover (INR Million)	Credit Size (INR Million)	Turnover (INR Million)	Credit Size (INR Million)	Turnover (INR Million)	Credit Size (INR Million)
Private Commercial Bank	1.5-50	0.2-1	50-200	5-150	200-2000	50-200
Non-Banking Finance Companies	0.05-1	1-5	5-25	0.3-5	10-1000	2.5-50

Source: MSMED Act

The micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSME) sector of the Indian economy is very large, with the most businesses and employees, and it is highly dynamic, with many businesses entering and leaving the market each year. By 2001, this sector of the Indian economy employed 24.932 million people across 10.521 enterprises, of which 5.808 were rural and the remaining urban, primarily in nonmetropolitan towns and semi-urban areas. The manufacturing sector accounted for close to 40% of all MSME enterprises, while the repairing and maintenance sector accounted for another 16%, with the total MSME gross output for 2001-02 coming in at ₹. 2,822 billion and export coming in at ₹. 141.79 billion. (Saleh, A.S. and Ndubisi, N.O, 2006)

The Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in India have evolved considerably since India's independence. Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) have undergone significant development. The MSME sector has evolved in scale and in the breadth of business activities throughout the years from being known to simply as the Small Scale Industries (SSI) sector in the 1960s and 1970s. MSMEs are widespread in India today across industries (manufacturing, trade, and services), contributing significantly to the remarkable economic progress of the nation. MSMEs have excelled at using domestic resources to produce high-quality goods and services over time, but they have also established themselves throughout India's core industries and in significant export markets. MSMEs have influenced a variety of topics, including entrepreneurship, industrial advancement, employment creation, and economic empowerment. The fact that almost 50.0% of MSMEs in India are held by underprivileged groups emphasizes the sector's inclusivity. Due to its low capital structure and strong labour absorption power, the industry has made a significant contribution to the industrialization of rural areas as well. The total transformation of India's economy from an agrarian one to an industrialised one continues to be largely fueled by the MSME sector. Governments all around India have since given MSMEs a variety of incentives. Other private and nonprofit groups have also helped MSMEs stay competitive in an increasingly globalised economic environment. The need for MSMEs to have access to capital, technological know-how, and training facilities to close the skill gap is expected to remain in the upcoming decade. (Baptiste-Cornelis, T. and Long, W., 2008)

Msme's Impact on the Development of the Rural Sector

The growth of small and medium-sized manufacturing businesses is largely responsible for the development of the rural sector. Rural residents face a number of difficulties, including unemployment, low income, a low standard of living, inadequate educational opportunities, and a lack of markets for their products. Although they have a variety of resources as raw materials, they lack the capital to transform those resources into finished commodities, which is why their society's ability to generate money is declining. Despite having a lot of raw materials, water resources, talent, and knowledge, educated and skilled youth moved to another district since there were no job facilities there. However, the MSME face numerous difficulties that make them ineffective and inefficient. Some MSMEs also bemoan the lengthy banking processes and challenges in obtaining bank loans. Others also voiced their displeasure with the banks' exorbitant interest rates. The majority of MSMEs also lack formal training in their fields of endeavour. High information asymmetry caused by MSMEs' lack of accounting records and inadequate financial statements, which makes it difficult for creditors and investors to access the credit worthiness of potential MSME proposals, is foremost among these issues, along with vulnerability to market fluctuations and high fold-up rates. Additionally, it is the cause of the ill units and MSME manufacturing sustainability problems. Additionally, as a result, there can be a significant funding blockage in the different fixed (capital) assets. These issues still exist in the MSME manufacturing sector,

particularly rural MSMEs. It is important to consider the role of DIC in the growth of MSMEs in the context of the federal government's "Make in India" initiative, as well as the resource limitations that MSMEs have faced for decades.

Inputs to these segments as demonstrated by data from the economy's somewhat out-of-date Input-Output tables, at factor costs, appear to show: low or declining use of machine tools and other industrial machinery; steep rise in energy consumption, especially of petroleum products; rise in other inputs from industry; and stagnation or moderate rise or in some cases even decline of inputs from agriculture. Rising energy costs coupled with a drop in the use of machine tools point to a slowdown in these industries' overall technological advancements. Reduced input consumption, as seen by a reduced value of factor inputs from agriculture, may signify a general deterioration of the materials-flow network between MSME and agricultural and is cause for considerable concern. This might also point to decreased relative prices, a sign of slower technological advancements in the agricultural and related industries. The agricultural input could then be obtained through non-price transactions from local unorganised markets or from networks of wholesalers and large dealers who supply input. Parallel to this, the proportional increase in prices of a variety of industrial inputs and feedstocks reflects both growing industrialization (in contrast to inputs from the agrarian system) and relative technological stagnation in comparison to major enterprises. (Moore, S.B. and Manring, S.L, 2009)

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A good literature review necessitates knowledge of the use of indexes and abstracts, the capacity to carry out thorough bibliographic searches, the capacity to organise the gathered data meaningfully, describe, critique, and relate each source to the topic of the enquiry, and present the organised review logically. Last but not least, but undoubtedly, is the capacity to correctly cite all sources mentioned. The literature review is provided below.

Dangayach and Deshmukh (2005) reported the findings of an exploratory survey on advanced manufacturing technologies (AMTs) administered in Indian small and medium enterprises (SMEs) of automobile, electronics, machinery, and process sectors. The objective of the survey is to assess the status of AMT, identify AMTs relevant to Indian SMEs, identify competitive priorities, AMT implementation criteria, and assess the degree of investment in AMTs. Responses from 122 companies are analyzed and presented. It is observed that Indian SMEs are giving the highest priority to quality and the least priority to flexibility. "Post-implementation evaluation" and "requirement analysis" AMT implementation steps have attracted least attention from Indian SMEs. This study is useful to others implementing AMT. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in Malaysian economy, and is considered to be the backbone of industrial development in the country. However, few studies examined their development, challenges and future prospects. **Saleh and Ndubisi (2006)** examined and analyzed the role of SMEs in different sectors as well as their major contribution to the economy (**Dangayach, G.S. and Deshmukh, S.G, 2005**) (**Saleh, A.S. and Ndubisi, N.O, 2006**)

"There appears to be growing consensus that Small Business Enterprises (SBEs) exert a major influence on the economy of Trinidad and Tobago. Baptiste-Cornelis and Long (2008) investigated how and to what extent small businesses influenced macroeconomic variables such as employment, growth and productivity in the important sectors of manufacturing and services. The study used a methodology that traverses the reader through a combination of various literatures, and theories coupled with relevant statistics on small business (**Baptiste-Cornelis, T. and Long, W., 2008**)

"**Moore and Manring (2009)**, discussed several different incentives for SMEs to optimize sustainability- (1) becoming valuable sustainable investment targets for larger firms; (2) creating highly competitive networks of sustainable SMEs in market spaces where large enterprises are less successful; (3) becoming highly efficient suppliers in global supply chains through sustainable practices. While, several successful models of the sustainable SME are evolving, it may be that networks of SMEs will become essential for addressing the systemic problems that underlie industrial ecology, enterprise resilience, and global supply chain sustainability. SMEs represent the majority of all enterprises, and rapidly evolving communication technologies allow for various routes of network formation (**Moore, S.B. and Manring, S.L, 2009**).

According to Khanka (2010) small enterprises have become one of the two important legs of industrial economy of India. That, of late, small enterprise sector has emerged as a vibrant sector in the Indian economy is indicated by its contribution in employment, income and exports. For example, they constitute over 90 per cent of total industrial units, account for around 80 per cent of the total industrial employment, and contribute nearly 39 per cent of the industrial production and around 33 per cent of the country's exports. (**Khanka, 2010**)

"The study of **Upadhyay et al (2011)** tried to explore the factors affecting implementation across the stages of ERP implementations using the responses from 98 MSMEs engaged in manufacturing activities. The minimum

number of factors explaining the maximum variance in data is determined using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The factor analysis is performed on SPSS with the principal component method using the Varimax Rotation Technique. The results of this study highlights four crucial factors that influence the ERP implementation process in the Indian MSME segment. Broadly, they may be summed up under the following heads: project execution competency; product and vendor perspective; organizational climate; and technical perspective. (Upadhyay, P., Jahanyan, S. and Dan, P.K, 2011)

Lahiri (2012), critically analyzed the definitional aspect of MSMEs and explore the opportunities enjoyed and the constraints faced by them in the era of globalization. Annual Average Growth rate (AAGR) has been used as the major statistical tool to compare the performances of MSMEs during pre and post liberalization process. The study results show that except marginal increase in growth rate in employment generation, the growth rate in other parameters is not encouraging during the liberalization period (J.Anuradha ; T.Parthiban, 2014)

Sharma et al., (2012) reviewed concisely the literature in this field and addresses in particular opportunities and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in rural areas. It examined the impact on women empowerment through micro entrepreneurship development and SHGs (Sharma, A., Dua, S. and Hatwa V, 2012).

Kiran (2013) attempted to understand as to how a small or micro undertaking can achieve success by adopting strategic decisions at the appropriate time. The case study of S.S. Fiber Tech Industries describes a successful journey of a micro industry wading through challenges for a decade into grow into a small industry by apt marketing decision and new channel strategies (Kiran, V.U., 2013).

“According to **Dey (2014)** the importance of MSME has been recognized in recent years in both developed and developing countries for its significant contribution in gratifying various socio-economic objectives such as higher growth of employment, output, promotion of exports and fostering entrepreneurship. They play a crucial role in the industrial development of any country. The MSME sector is an important pillar of Indian economy as it contributes greatly to growth of Indian economy (Dey, 2014).

“**Rajesh et al., (2015)** observed that micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) all over the world have been recognised as silent drivers of a nation’s economy. Their role in the economic and social development of a country is well established. The MSME sector is a breeding ground of entrepreneurship, often driven by individual creativity and innovation at grass root level and shows dynamism in terms of Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) have been accepted as an engine for economic growth and equitable development (Rajesh, P., Singla, S. and Gupta, A, 2015).

“Gupta and Barua (2016) identified important enablers of technological innovation in the context of Indian MSMEs. Extant literature review and expert judgment are used to identify enablers of technological innovation. A novel multi-criteria decision making technique called best worst method is applied to find out most important enablers among these. Research results indicate project resources and capabilities; technical know-how of entrepreneurs and government policies as most important enablers contributing significantly towards technological development of MSMEs (Gupta, H. and Barua, M.K, 2016).

An ongoing debate in employment policy is whether promoting small and medium enterprises creates jobs. **Martin et al., (2017)** used the elimination of small-scale industry (SSI) promotion in India to address this question. Authors identified the consequences for employment growth, investment, output, productivity, and wages of dismantling India’s SSI reservations. They exploit variation in the timing of dereservation across products and also measure the long-run impact of national SSI policy changes using variation in pretreatment exposure at the district level (Martin, L.L., Nataraj, S. and Harrison, A.E, 2017).

III. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology and particular steps taken to carry out the current investigation are presented in this section. This covers details on the research design, sample selection, creation of the research instrument, mode of data collection, and techniques for data analysis. One of the rural districts was chosen as the study region for the current study.

Population and Size of Sample

The study’s target population, or universe, is a comprehensive collection of all units. Accordingly, depending on the goal and scope of the study, the population can be made up of all the units in the nation, those in a specific geographic area, or members of a particular ethnic or socioeconomic group. A population could also be made up of non-human entities like farms, homes, or commercial buildings. Thus, the entire universe of MSMEs was taken into consideration. 175 MSMEs in total were chosen for the current study’s data generation.

Data Collection, Sampling Technique, and Reliability

In the current study, Clustered Random Sampling approach was used. Randomly chosen MSME units were taken from each cluster. A questionnaire was created as an instrument for data gathering. From the chosen sample, data were gathered regarding this designed instrument.

The instrument's test-retest reliability was discovered to be 0.85, which is sufficient for the reliability required for data collecting.

Statistical Tools

For the analysis of data various statistical tools will be used in this study such as

1. Graph and Chart will be used for presentation
2. Cronbach’s Alpha test
3. Association measurement: Correlation Coefficient and regression analysis
4. Chi-Square significance test
5. One direction ANOVA

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

The major part of this research paper is data analyzing and interpretation for the collected data using proper research Methodology for those collected respondents profile of this studies. The analyzing the role of Micro Small Medium Enterprise for economic development of rural India for that purpose researcher tries to analyze the types of size industries of MSMEs, and the profile of workers and employed in the particular industries, and what types of Training is required for improving productivity, Quality control as import and part of industries, and which types of Problems faced by industries for working higher labor problems as well as Financial assistance, and Government policies.

Table No: 2: Type of Industry

Type of Industry	Frequency	Percentage
Medium	02	1.1 %
Small	112	64.0 %
Micro	61	34.9 %
Total	175	100 %
Chi sq	Df	Sig.
38.426	2	<0.001

Chart:1 Types of Industry

The above table no.2 and chart no.1 is highlights different types of industries for collecting respondents for this study purpose. The majority of the small industry is total no of 112 (64.0%) respectively, as compare Micro level industry is total no of 61 (34.9%) and rest of medium level industry is 02 (1.1%).

Table No.3: Workers Employed in Industries

Workers	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 25	163	93.1 %
More than 25	12	6.9 %
Total	175	100 %

Chi sq	Df	Sig.
130.291	1	<0.000

Chart No.2: Workers Employed in Industries

Table No.3 and Chart No.2 showing the details regarding workers employed in different types of MSMEs total of 175 respondents out of 163 (93.1 %) Less than 25 workers need and more than 25 respondents is 12(6.9%) worked in employed in different industries.

Table No.4: Training to Employees for Improving Productivity

Training to Employees	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	98	56.0 %
Agree	65	37.1 %
Disagree	12	6.9 %
Total	175	100 %
Chi sq	Df	Sig.
103.149	2	<0.001

Chart No.3: Training to Employees for Improving Productivity

Above table no.4 and chart no.3 opinions about the requirement for training to employees in the improving productivity in respective industries 98 (56.0%) respondent strongly agree , 65 (37.1%) respondents Agree, 12 (6.9%) respondents Disagree regarding need for training to employees for improving better quality of productivity.

Table.5: Quality Control as an important part of Industry

Quality Control	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	85	48.6 %
Agree	78	44.6 %
Disagree	12	6.9 %
Total	175	100 %
Chi sq	Df	Sig.
103.149	2	<0.001

Chart No.4: Quality Control as an Import and part of Industry

The quality control is a very important part of every industry table no.5 and chart no.6 showing the opinion 85(48.6%) respondents Strongly Agree , 78 (44.6%) respondents Agree, and 12(6.9%) Disagree.

Table No-6: Problems Faced by Industry

Problems faced	Frequency	Percentage
Finance	70	40.0 %
Labor	34	19.4 %
Marketing	21	12.0 %
Technical	50	28.6 %
Total	175	100 %

Chart No.5: Problems Faced by Industry

The above table no.6 and chart no.5 showing the problems faced by the industry, the majority 70 (40.0%) respondents face financial problems, 34 (19.4) respondents face skilled labor, 21(12.0%) respondents face marketing problems, 50 (28.6%) respondent face technical problems by their respective industries.

Table No-7: Higher Labor Cost as a Problem

Labor Cost	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	85	48.6 %
Agree	78	44.6 %
Disagree	12	6.9 %
Total	175	100 %
Chi sq	Df	Sig.
69.411	2	<0.001

Chart No.6: Higher Labor Cost as a Problem

The above table no.7 and chart no.6 face the problems of high labor costs in their respective industries, 85 (48.6 %) respondent opinion is Strongly Agree, 78(44.6 %) respondent opinion is Agree, and 12 (6.9%) respondent opinion is Disagree.

Table No-8: Financial Assistance

Govt. Provides Financial Assistance	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	115	65.7 %
No	45	25.7 %
Somewhat	15	8.6 %
Total	175	100 %
Chi sq	Df	Sig.
41.434	2	<0.001

Chart No.7: Financial Assistance

The MSME unit’s government provides financial assistance for promoting such types of industries for nation-building. The above table no.8 and chart no.7 highlight a total no of 115 (65.7%) respondents who recorded Yes, the government provides financial assistance for setup industries, and the rest of the 45(25%) said No, and reaming 15 (8.6%) respondents response is recorded somewhat.

Table No-9: Government Policies

Govt. Policies are favorable to Industry	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	133	76.0 %
No	18	10.3 %
Cant Say	24	13.7 %
Total	175	100 %
Chi sq	Df	Sig.
41.434	2	<0.001

Chart No.8: Government Policies

Any industrial development needs to clear and clean government policies to the favorable for industries. The results of government policies in the favor of 133(76.0%) respondents who recorded a response in favor of government policies, 18(10.3%) industries recorded a response as unfavorable, and the rest of 24 (13.7%) respondents recorded their opinion as cant say.

V. CONCLUSION

- ✓ Majority of MSME industries had less than 25 workers.
- ✓ Regular training to employee working in MSME industries help in improving the productivity of industries.
- ✓ Quality control is an important part of the MSME industry.
- ✓ MSME industries faced finance-related problems, labor-related problems as well as marketing and technical problems.
- ✓ Raising labor costs is a problem for the majority of MSME industries.
- ✓ Current government policies are favorable for the development of MSME industries.
- ✓ Government provides financial assistance to MSME industries.
- ✓ Government should ensure that there should be no power cut-off for MSMEs in the region.

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